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Technology Assessment

at the Swiss Science and Technology Council

PubliForum "Electricity and Society"

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Citizen Panel Report

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Foreword

by Klaus Hug (president of the TA-Steering Committee)

The first Swiss PubliForum met with an overwhelming response, both in the media and - above all - from the parties involved. The Citizen Panel, and all who were involved in the accompanying group and the preparation team or figured as guests, donated time and energy to the event with a commitment and an enthusiasm above all expectation. One could even speak of a risky adventure: it was not at all clear in advance, if the Citizen Panel's work would lead to success or not.

Here we present the first results of three intensive week-ends: the Citizen Panel's Report on "Electricity and Society". In this document, 27 Swiss citizens have recorded their opinions on the future of our electricity supply system. Solutions are sought without making claims on having found the ultimate recipe. The recommendations are the result of an assessment made by a representative cross-section of the public - one could almost say "the voice of the people". They reflect not only the public's apprehensions and worries, but also their ideas and desires.

The TA-Steering Committee is pleased about the success of this first Swiss Citizens Panel. We feel that it has now been confirmed that PubliFori can make an important contribution to encouraging objectivity and supporting a relaxed relationship between science and technology and the general public.

1. PubliForum "Electricity and Society": A new perspective

Introduction by the TA-Programme

1.1. Which tasks are to be performed by PubliForum "Electricity and Society"?

The future of our energy policy is happening now. It is being forged today, somewhere on the narrow ridge between yesterday and tomorrow. New research work is being carried out which will lead to promising technological developments. The changes accompanying globalisation and liberalisation of the electricity market arouse numerous hopes, but also a great many uncertainties. Political aspects are becoming more and more complex: several new bills are presently being discussed or are in preparation (Energy Act, CO₂-Act, Nuclear Energy Act, Ecological Tax Reform). Apart from this legislation, the general public will be asked to vote on various popular initiatives (Energy-Environment-Initiative, Solar-Initiative, Moratorium Plus, Opting out of Nuclear Energy).

By bringing about thirty Citizens from the whole of Switzerland to participate in a 'round table' discussion, PubliForum "Electricity and Society" seeks to introduce a new dimension into current and future debates, which are very often characterised solely by facts and figures and by the particular interests of the parties affected. In the course of several days of intensive work, the citizens participating in the PubliForum "Electricity and Society" had the opportunity to contribute their own personal experience and their day-to-day worries and expectations in the hope that these will be taken into consideration when formulating future Swiss energy policy. In addition, the discussions which took place between experts and citizens (and which form the basis of this report) should provide a contribution to the open, public debate on an electricity supply system which will be able to face up to the future.

1.2. What is PubliForum all about?

The PubliForum organised by the Swiss TA-Programme is built on the "Consensus-Conference"-model developed in Denmark and since adopted in several European countries (including - amongst others - the Netherlands, the United Kingdom and Norway). The PubliForum "Electricity and Society" is the first ever Consensus-Conference carried out in Switzerland.

The Consensus-Conference instrument was developed in order to provide the general public with an opportunity to take part in decisions on technology policy. Up till now, it has been especially used with reference to questions in the fields of biological and genetic engineering. The Consensus-Conferences open promising perspectives with respect to the reactivation of democratic debate on technical topics.

The procedure is based on the following method: a panel of citizens - men and women "from the street" - confront experts who they have previously selected with questions on controversial technical topics. Subsequently, the Citizen Panel summarises its main conclusions and recommendations in a report, which is then presented to the Federal Assembly, decision-makers in politics and administration, interested parties affected and the media. As technological developments challenge us with topics which exceed pure scientific consideration, the definition of the term "expert" was widened: anyone concerned with the topic being discussed from the point of view of science, politics or economics can be called in as an expert.

1.3. PubliForum "Electricity and Society": the main stages

The PubliForum represents the culmination of almost a whole year's work needed by the TA-Programme to prepare and put together the necessary components necessary for a real debate between citizens and experts

The first step was to put together an "Accompanying-Group" which would aid and support the TA-Office in its activities. In this way, experts in energy questions, representatives of interest groups and specialists for participative processes could guarantee that the various phases of the PubliForum were correctly implemented. For example, the actual form of the PubliForum - and especially the freedom granted to the participating citizens when organising the debates and defining the form of the report - were the result of intensive discussions in the Accompanying Group, as was the method of choosing the citizens taking part.

Great efforts were taken to ensure that the Citizen Panel were presented with a list of experts which was as comprehensive as possible. This guaranteed that it could choose along with specialists from different areas of science, technology and economy, also representatives of the public authorities and interest groups. Several hundred Swiss experts were contacted and further specialists were sought in other countries. In order to make the Panel's choice easier, a short profile was written on each expert who had agreed to take part in the PubliForum event.

The selection of the citizens who were to take part in the PubliForum ran in parallel to the search for experts. Potential candidates were recruited in the framework of an opinion survey and also via newspaper advertisements. 27 people were selected out of the over 60 who enrolled at the TA-Programme office. In this way a panel was put together which was well-balanced in respect to age, language, sex and profession.

As is done in the Consensus-Conferences in other countries, the participants of the PubliForum were able to inform themselves in advance on important issues and the difficulties encountered in formulating energy policy thanks to a documentation especially prepared for the PubliForum and previously okayed by the Accompanying-Group. Subsequently, the Citizen Panel had the opportunity to extend their knowledge during two preparatory weekends, during which they also chose about twenty experts and formulated the questions they would want to ask them.

The main findings and recommendations made by the citizens participating in the PubliForum are summed up in the report now in your hands. It is based on the answers given by the experts and the personal experience and hopes of the citizens. The report was written completely independently and the most of the opinions and suggestions are shared by all members of the panel. The intention was not to try to make definitive conclusions: the PubliForum report is meant to trigger further discussion in interested circles and the public.

All discussions carried out in the framework of the PubliForum were moderated by a professional moderator. His main job was to ensure that the dialogue could be carried out freely, without any form of external influence and under conditions which allowed all opinions to be brought up. Difficulties, which might have been caused by teamwork involving citizens from three different language areas, were avoided by using the valuable support of interpreters during the discussions and translators during the final editing of the report.

1.4. Outcome and outlook

The PubliForum is to be evaluated by a third party, in order to investigate if the dialogue between citizens and experts was carried out in a transparent and honest way and if the process corresponded to the expectations of the organisers. Looking back on what has been produced, we are proud to note that our efforts were not in vain, even though the final evaluation has not yet been concluded. Although a group of 27 citizens cannot be statistically representative of the whole of Switzerland, we were astonished by the variety and broadness of mind represented by the participants of the Citizen Panel. We were equally impressed by the commitment shown by the participants during three week-ends of unpaid hard work.

In addition, the citizens were in a position to recognise the most important questions posed in spite of the complex matter and, in particular, were able to formulate their assessments and recommendations in a subtle and sophisticated way.

Last but not least, The PubliForum supports us in our intentions to increasingly provide frameworks in which the dialogue between experts and "the man and woman on the street" can be organised. On the one hand, the participating specialists were able to justify their arguments to the citizens, thus helping prevent any somewhat hasty or too simplified assessments being made. On the other hand, the experts were forced to consider the citizens' hopes and fears in their points of view. These manifest themselves in particular in wanting to leave behind an environment fit for future generations whilst still wanting their needs as consumers and as part of the working population to be met.

The PubliForum represents a first step in the direction of bringing together two widely separated worlds, and we hope that the future will bring further opportunities for dialogue and exchange of ideas and thus contribute to the increasing democratisation of the discussions surrounding science and the choice of appropriate technologies.

The Citizen Panel

2. The Citizen Panel

<i>Family Name</i>	<i>First Name</i>	<i>Town / City</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Profession</i>
Bamert	Markus	Schübelbach-Berne	33	Cabinet-maker, in training
Bippert	Jean-François	La Chaux-de-Fonds	62	Senior citizen
Brändle-Brauchle	Rita	Jona	56	Housewife, clerk
Caratsch	Marie-Theres	Schwyz	34	Architect
Cherpillod	Lotty	Cortébert	60	Housewife
Eggenberger	Hans	Buchs	73	Senior citizen
Fedier	Patrizia	Zurich	70	Physical therapist
Forrer	Athit	Riedwil	17	Apprentice clerk
Habenicht	Martin	Kerzers	33	Electrical engineer HTL
Köpfer	Rolf	Thalwil	48	Businessman (Private coach)
Kurmann	Carlo	Gordola	46	Architect STS
Mabillard	Pierrette	Chippis	50	Employee
Marcos	Luis	Eclépens	27	Architect

<i>Family Name</i>	<i>First Name</i>	<i>Town / City</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Profession</i>
Mettier	Thomas	Zurich	26	Scientist ETH
Möhl	Margareta	Berne	43	Secretary
Oggier	Jean-Marie	Geneva	45	Clerk
Paloschi	Pierluigi Gianbattista	Berne	60	Freelance journalist GRJLP
Perret-Moser	Maryse-A.	La Chaux-de-Fonds	64	Inter-cultural worker (senior citizen)
Putschkar	Pierre	Cortailod	52	Disabled pensioner (ex- aircraft mechanic)
Schalit	Tobias	Burgdorf	21	Student
Scollo	Valérie Elena	Geneva	20	Student
Stutz	Lydia	Schaffhausen	65	Midwife, senior citizen
Trüssel	Peter	Berne	57	Civil servant
Walpen	Alexandra	Berne	22	Student HSL
Wasem	Werner	Walliswil b.W.	38	Training manager
Wintsch	Erich	Oberwil-Lieli	48	Management consultant
Zanetti	Giancarla	Berne	39	Part-time comics artist, editor, speaker, unemployed

3. The Citizen Panel's Report

3.1. Foreword

This report does not pretend to present solutions to the problems encountered in "electricity and society". It reflects the wishes, fears and ideas of the Citizen Panel. The questions we have raised only cover a part of this complex topic. And it was, of course, not possible for us to reach a consensus of opinion on all questions, neither during the intensive discussions nor after questioning experts. Especially in regard to the question of "incentive taxes", a small minority was not able to identify itself with the recommendations presented. The minority opinion is that price increases caused by an additional tax are not acceptable in an economy marked by a period of recession.

3.2. Conclusions

Basically, our main concern is to meet our future electricity needs in a sustainable way. In this context, "Sustainable" means that future generations will still have a basis for their existence unaffected by problematical wastes and emissions affecting the climate.

Since nuclear power does not in our opinion fulfil the criteria of sustainability, we strive for the fastest possible withdrawal from the nuclear energy programme. As energy from fossil sources also does not fulfil these criteria, we see that only two main lines of attack are possible in order to meet future electricity needs:

- Further propagation of renewable energy forms (including hydro-power).
- General energy conservation measures and optimum use of electrical energy.

The forthcoming liberalisation and the freedom of choice connected with it can play an important part as an incentive to meet these goals, but only in association with complete cost-reality and price transparency. Since, in the short term, external costs will not be reflected in prices, the introduction of an incentive tax simultaneously with the liberalisation of the electricity market is imperative.

The resulting price structures alone will not be sufficient to assure that renewable energy forms will be propagated fast enough to attain the share in electricity generation desired, which means that they have to be specially promoted. Several different technical solutions are already available today, although at different levels of development. The political determination to support a fast break-through is, however, lacking. In this respect, every citizen can make his or her own contribution.

We are all also requested to make a contribution through our own personal responsibility and initiative when it comes to energy conservation, in order to make full use of the potential for savings which is already to be seen. These goals can, however, only be reached by means of open information from all sides and an honest dialogue between those involved.

We are quite aware that we have a long and stony way in front of us if we intend to reach our goal of having a completely sustainable electricity supply. As, at the moment, no short-cuts are in sight, we find it very important that we set off immediately - and the report in your hands is the first step.

The Citizen Panel questions experts during the hearing in the National Council Chamber

3.3. Electricity and environment

3.3.1. Question

Who can guarantee an "intact" environment with respect to the risks involved in generating electricity? Which ways and means (such as financing, steering instruments, legislation etc.) are available in order to guarantee an "intact" environment?

3.3.2. Main experts consulted

- Chaim Nissim (Contratom, Green Party)
- Silva Semadeni (National Councillor, Social Democrats)

3.3.3. Summary of experts' answers

Independent of the existence of man, nature is in an on-going process of development, which brings forth various environmental states at various times. This is why one should speak of sustainable development rather than of an "intact" environment.

Sustainable development is defined as meeting the needs of the present-day generation without putting the chances of future generations at risk. Although the consequences of the greenhouse effect will have to be coped with by future generations, the nuclear option is no alternative as the final disposal of nuclear wastes is not solved. A real alternative would be the promotion of renewable energy forms, whose costs could be lowered by incentive taxes.

The following means are available to help attain sustainable development in the area of electricity generation:

- Legislation: e.g. Energy Article, Environmental protection law, Law on the protection of lakes and rivers, nuclear regulations etc. The Federal Council and The Federal Assembly are responsible for minimising risks, the application of

legislation is the job of federal government, cantons and local authorities. Important instruments in this area are environment compatibility reviews, the rights of appeal of conservation groups as well as public rights (popular initiative and referendum).

- Citizens' Action groups (e.g. petitions).
- Marketplace economical instruments: true costing and incentive taxes are important, as is providing market transparency through, for example, product labelling.

3.3.4. Citizens' position

The political control instruments suggested by the experts are important. They do not, though, exempt us from our own personal responsibilities:

- The individual can take a lot of influence depending on his or her consumer behaviour.
- Environmental responsibility has to be perceived in the areas of political engagement in environmental questions and when voting.

We demand, therefore, that specific and transparent information be made - also from the politicians' side.

Also, we demand that trade and industry take the consequences of their own special responsibility, for example by increasing investments in energy efficiency. In the consumer area we require more transparency, e.g. through labelling. Here, consumer protection organisations are faced with a challenge.

In many areas, there are no solutions available yet. We need citizens with a sense of courage.

3.4. Disposal of nuclear wastes

3.4.1. Question

How safely and with what responsibility is the disposal of radioactive wastes and the nuclear power plant shut down later to be dealt with? How can the general public contribute to a solution?

3.4.2. Main experts consulted

- Roland Naegelin (President of the National Commission on Nuclear Safety)
- Piet Zuidema (Nagra, departmental head of Nuclear Technology and Safety)

3.4.3. Summary of experts' answers

The damage potential represented by the final disposal of radioactive waste is lower than that incurred during normal operation of nuclear power stations. At worst, there may be local effects but no catastrophe. The risk of having local effects is very low, however.

The question of final disposal is scientifically solved, deciding on a site is a purely political question. No final disposal site can be built against the will of the general public. A disposal site must be supported by all citizens, meaning that collective thinking is necessary.

According to the experts the costs of disposal are covered and included in the price of electricity. According to another expert, this is only true under optimum conditions. Today's intermediate storage sites are safe, as they are permanently under supervision.

3.4.4. Citizens' position

We have to solve the disposal problem, we cannot turn the clocks back. For this we need a final disposal site in Switzerland.

We believe the experts, when they say that, in research, they doing their best and are looking for the greatest possible safety. Absolute safety can, however, never be guaranteed. The resulting feeling of unease leads to the situation that the Citizen Panel looks at the risks in a different way than the experts and puts up resistance. On top of this, experts and citizens speak in different tongues and thus do not - or do not want to - understand each other. The site problem is in our opinion not only a political question, but also one of differences concerning risk perception and communication cultures.

Although, at the moment, existing wastes cannot be definitively stored, waste is continually being produced. But as no replacement for nuclear power is in sight, we are not able to come to an agreement on whether this problem is to be solved by the premature closing-down of nuclear power stations. Also, the readiness to accept possible shortcomings differs among the Citizens Panel.

For us, it is difficult to judge if the costs of waste disposal are really fully covered.

3.5. Ethics

3.5.1. Question

Shouldn't an energy production and supply system consider ethical principles?

3.5.2. Main experts consulted

- Joel Jakubec (President of the Appeal of Geneva APAG)
- Regula Gysler (Physicians for the Environment)

3.5.3. Summary of experts' answers

Generally, ethics can be considered as being "the society's ethical and moral fundamentals as a whole"

3.5.4. Citizens' position

Ethics are often closely coupled with upbringing and are therefore many-faceted.

The expert has wider knowledge at his disposal than the man or woman on the street. This fact should not, however, represent a free pass to take greater liberties and make decisions on behalf of society.

Ethics must become an integral part of our day-to-day life as a result of our individual activities.

If we produce environmentally dangerous wastes, we must assume the responsibility for them and store them ourselves.

"Primum nil nocere"

Wealth (personal or that of a country) does not legitimate making contamination.

Energy can be considered as a heritage which every person can lay claims on, but also has to protect.

Ethics are part of man's thoughts and conscience. They are developed continuously as new problems crop up.

Science should not serve profit, but, first of all, serve man.

We have therefore to practice differentiation and weighing up.

3.5.5. Suggestion

We consider it to be desirable that an Ethics Committee states its opinion on relevant energy-policy projects. Those politically responsible would be required to take the standpoint of the Ethics Commission into consideration in all decision making.

3.6. Energy conservation

3.6.1. Question

What possibilities are available in order to reduce electricity consumption? Which methods can we use and which measures must be put into practice?

- a) Which technical means are available today?
- b) What means of influence do we have to increase peoples' sensitivity on the subject and motivate them to change their behaviour?
- c) Which political and economical frames of reference would help contribute to the savings?

3.6.2. Main experts consulted

- Peter Marbert (Deputy Head of Infrastructure Department, Novartis Services AG, Basel)
- Toni Püntener (Zürich Energy Consulting)

3.6.3. Summary of experts' answers

It is quite clear that this aspect must under no circumstances be ignored.

The hypothesis of one of the experts, who considers it possible to reduce present-day electricity consumption by 75%, is especially interesting. This vision seems for us to be absolutely practicable.

- Existing technical ways and means by which peoples' sensitivity to the subject can be increased and their behaviour can be altered.
- Low consumption products are already available, as proved by the examples quoted by the specialists. This is valid, too, for motivation measures.

3.6.4. Citizens' position

All currently available ways and means have to be put into action and new methods must be developed.

Changes on the technical apparatus side and modification of consumer behaviour allow large electricity savings to be made.

In the technical area, very ambitious regulations will have to be laid down in the short term. Manufacturers should meet the challenge to reduce the power consumption of all current conventional electric and electronic apparatus (TVs, refrigerators etc.) by 30%. Appliances meeting these demands would be awarded an eco-quality label.

3.6.5. Suggestions

Communication should be intensified in order to make those products and technologies better known to the wider public which are not extravagant in the use of power (technical products, buildings etc.)

The use of innovative goods should be encouraged through subsidised exhibitions and well-targeted information. The aim is to awake the interest of companies who are prepared to provide support for such products from the development stage up to the marketing phase.

Citizens must be provided with the possibility of participating in an "innovation-stock-exchange" which would allow them to financially support projects on a voluntary basis.

It is desirable that:

- Private households, industry, and also public and private transportation should find solutions which allow the more efficient use of electricity.
- Information should be given more professionally and be specifically directed towards the general public. (Not solely selective information campaigns should be carried out, but rather the continuous information flow for the public should be guaranteed).
- Sensitisation programmes for schools should be developed (schoolchildren would carry the information home to their parents).
- Clear labelling of appropriate products should be introduced.

Further, we would like that:

- After the PubliForum is concluded, TA would set up an Internet Homepage with a mailbox for suggestions from the general public.
- A condensed catalogue be published which would allow citizens the best possible access to information on energy topics.

Finally we suggest that:

- An institution be given an assignment to calculate energy quotas for private households and industry, as well as for traffic and transportation networks. Consumers who exceed the quotas should be more heavily taxed whilst others, who can bring evidence of energy savings, would pay less.

3.7. Renewable and alternative energy

3.7.1. Question

From which date on and to what proportion can future electricity consumption be met by renewable or alternative energy technologies?

- a) Would the renewal of turbines bring us a substantial improvement of capacity? And if so, how much?
- b) What are the prospects and risks of geothermal energy (e.g. "Hot-dry-rock" process)?
- c) What is the current state-of-the-art in research into photo-synthesis (specifically: the Graetzel-Cell)?
- d) Which new methods are available for the storage and transport of electrical energy (e.g. superconductors, new types of batteries etc.)?
- e) Are there new processes for energy production not well known to the general public? What is the state-of-the-art?
- f) What are the criteria used for the support and (financial) promotion of renewable / alternative energy sources? Who defines them? Who makes the decisions on which technologies are supported and promoted?

3.7.2. Main experts consulted

- Markus Häring (Häring Geo-Projects)
- Fritjof Staiss (Centre for Solar Energy and Hydrogen Research (ZSW), Stuttgart)
- Hans-Ulrich Schärer (Swiss Federal Office of Energy, renewable energy)
- Pierre Lehmann (Association for environmental studies SEDE SA)

3.7.3. Summary of experts' answers

It must be realised that today 60% of electricity is produced from renewable resources (hydro-power) and 40% by nuclear power

Alternative energy, apart from hydro-power, contributes only to a small degree to Swiss electricity production.

- a) *Improvement of turbine capacity*: Yes, although the room for improvement in hydro-power is only a few percent.

According to one expert, small hydro plant could provide a considerable contribution. Many small streams make a wide river!

- b) *Chances and risks of geothermal energy*: Up to now, no risks are known, as geothermal energy utilises the natural warmth of the earth (this can be directly used, without having to process it). Certain opinions are voiced, which refer to a cooling-down of the earth, but this will not happen to any great extent.

According to the specialist in geothermics, the big chances lie in the extraordinary potential for development: geothermal energy is available everywhere and at all times, is environmentally compatible, generates no waste products and does not have to be stored.

Based on realistic assumptions, the following forecast can be made: by the year 2050, 20% of our electricity demand may well be met by this energy source.

- c) *State of the research into the Graetzel Cell*: The cell is still in the development stage. It may well make a noticeable reduction in production costs possible, in comparison with photovoltaics.

- d) *New possibilities for storage and transport*: According to one of the experts questioned, the most well known storage media are mountain reservoirs and batteries. Great hopes are set in hydrogen and other chemical energy carriers.

For the transport of electricity, high-temperature superconductors are being looked at.

- e) *New, up to now unknown processes*: Apart from geothermics and Graetzel Cell quoted above, no further revolutionary solutions for our country were mentioned.

- f) *Criteria for promotion*: On this question, we were given no real answers by the experts. The Federal Energy Commission took up the following position: "In order to be able to set priorities in research and development, the Federal Office of Energy uses recommendations made by the Federal Energy Commission. These are based on the general plan for the period 1996 - 1999 which was approved by the Federal Council. The aim is to provide more-or-less constant

funding for renewable energy, whereby pilot and demonstration projects are to be especially promoted. Up till now, we have kept to these guidelines, which still seem acceptable to us".

3.7.4. Citizens' position

It will probably not be possible to replace nuclear power generation by alternative technologies in the short term. The renewable technologies show great promise, however, and therefore should be developed further.

- a) *Improvement of turbine capacity:* We are of the opinion that in the light of the present-day situation these investments must be made. Every small percentage counts!
- b) *Chances and risks of geothermal energy:* This solution provides a good outlook for the future, has several advantages and, as it seems, few disadvantages for the environment.
- c) *Criteria for promotion:* We were surprised which modest amounts of money are dedicated to promising research projects. Here it is necessary that something be done. More funds and more resources must be invested in the promotion of these promising research projects.

3.7.5. Synthesis

Certain solutions are already available, others are yet to be developed and implemented. What is missing are the determination and the resources, both on the political as well as at economic levels.

According to various prognoses, we are fairly assured that the renewable forms of energy will soon play an important part in meeting our demands for power.

Teamwork during one of the preparatory week-ends.

3.8. Liberalisation of the electricity market

3.8.1. Question

What are the consequences of liberalisation for the consumer?

- a) Who wins? Who loses?
- b) Can political influence still be taken?
- c) What happens to renewable energy?
- d) How can the security of supply be guaranteed everywhere?
- e) How can the passing on of the costs of so-called "stranded investments" to the consumer be justified?

3.8.2. Main experts consulted

- Georg Erdmann (TU Berlin, Head of the Expert Group for Energy Systems)
- Jean-François Dupont (General secretary of Communauté Electricité Romande)
- Rolf Wüstenhagen (Scientific collaborator, Institute for Business and Ecology, HSG)

3.8.3. Summary of experts' answers

- a) *Who wins, who loses:* The national economy as a whole will win in the long term, since, as a result of the competition, no more resources will be squandered (lower electricity prices will result from this) and the competitiveness of Switzerland will be raised - all experts agree on this point. Liberalisation has the peculiarity, that one cannot foresee all details in advance, as it takes on a momentum of its own.

In the short term, not all will profit: on the one hand the private consumers, since they only benefit at a later point in time, and on the other certain sectors of business (amongst others the electricity utilities themselves and certain local communities), which will of course be affected by these structural changes.

- b) *Possibilities for political influence*: Basically, all citizens have the normal democratic instruments at their disposal (popular initiative, referendum, rights of appeal by associations, environmental impact assessment) in order to be able to assert influence. This is valid for the Electricity Market Act as well as also for future bills such as the Solar-Initiative, the Energy & Environment Initiative etc. On top of this, state departments are responsible for the granting of concessions and operating permits. State influence on production costs should - as is demanded for - be eliminated. But, if incentive taxes are introduced, the state will still have a considerable influence on end-user prices.
- c) *The positioning of renewable energy sources*: The experts are unanimous that the use of renewable energy will be substantially handicapped unless supporting measures are taken, as it will be even less competitive than today because of the expected lower prices. In addition, the present-day glut of electricity in Europe causes further difficulties.
- d) *Secure supply for all*: A secure supply consists on the one hand of a guaranteed connection to the electricity grid and on the other hand of an uninterrupted supply of electricity. According to the experts, these aims can best be reached by an independent, monopolistic grid-company, which must fulfil appropriate conditions of service. In particular cases, off-grid solutions are to be expected and permitted for cost reasons.
- e) *Passing on the costs of "stranded investments"*: The demand for compensation for stranded investments is basically justified by the unforeseen changes in the general situation, as represented by the creation of a competitive situation through liberalisation. There is disagreement, however, if this compensation is to be paid at all, or how much will be paid by whom. From an economics point of view, though, it is becoming apparent that compensation will best be made - if at all - by a one-off payment rather than putting a surcharge on electricity prices.

3.8.4. Citizens' position

Basically, the Citizen Panel considers a form of liberalisation which brings transparency, disentangles interests and provides a competitive situation with freedom of choice for all to be desirable and advantageous. Approval is dependent, however, on being able to ensure that energy-economy measures are not affected and that, in Switzerland, renewable energy forms can still be promoted and supported. With respect to this point,

it is considered essential that a substantial incentive tax be levied, possibly complemented by a mix of further supporting measures such as guaranteed grid access for producers of electricity from renewable sources, quota regulations and electricity "stock-exchanges".

The Citizen Panel considers it to be unreasonable that private customers and others with low electricity consumption will only enjoy their freedom of choice ten years after the legislation comes into effect. We believe that this can be achieved within five years if, for example, local electricity utilities are required to represent the interests of their end-users (i.e. local inhabitants).

The Citizens Panel requests that renewable energy's share (not including hydro-power) should exceed 10% of the whole consumption within ten years.

Any cases of hardship caused by the liberalisation should be dealt with directly and individually, without complicating or watering down the basic principle of liberalisation.

Domestic resources - especially in mountain areas - are to be supported by appropriate measures.

3.9. External costs

3.9.1. Question

How can all costs incurred, including external ones, be integrated in the price of electricity?

- a) What would the consequences be, as far as price structures are concerned?
- b) Is "Cost-reality" applicable from a social, political and scientific point of view?

3.9.2. Main experts consulted

- Rudolf Strahm (National Councillor, Social Democrats)
- Stefan Hirschberg (Paul Scherrer Institute)

3.9.3. Summary of experts' answers

All experts agree that this can only be reached by means of an incentive tax on the electricity price.

The experts cannot agree on the question of the exact calculation of external costs (evaluation, after-effects)

- a) *Pricing*: No expert could answer this question!
- b) *Cost-reality*: Yes, basically possible.

3.9.4. Citizens' position

It is a question of political will, if external costs are to be included in electricity prices or not.

It is our opinion that all costs, including external costs, should be integrated in electricity prices by means of an incentive tax.

That part of the incentive tax income earmarked for external costs must be used to aliment a fund for covering damage caused by after-effects.

Discussion in full swing

3.10. Incentive tax, Energy taxation

3.10.1. Question

What influence would an electricity price increase caused by the introduction of an incentive tax or other forms of energy taxation have on the job situation? How would the competitiveness of Swiss businesses be affected?

3.10.2. Main experts consulted

- Rolf Wüstenhagen (scientific collaborator, Institute for Business and Ecology, HSG)
- Rudolf Strahm (National Councillor, Social Democrats)

3.10.3. Summary of experts' answers

Most experts agreed that a price increase for electricity would have a neutral or positive influence on the job situation.

One expert from industry, however, was of the opinion that an electricity price increase would have a negative effect on the Swiss workplace.

Structural change has now been experienced for some time and will not be especially influenced by the introduction of incentive taxes.

There are several opinions on how the revenue from the incentive tax should be used.

3.10.4. Citizens' position

The majority of the PubliForum is of the opinion that the competitiveness of Swiss business will be influenced positively by an incentive tax. The introduction of an incentive tax should be arranged as fast as possible, and, depending on electricity consumption, increased step by step. We plead for a distribution of the revenues of the incentive tax. Disagreement on the use of revenues must not delay its introduction!

Revenues must be used for specific purposes, which are to be finally regulated in the framework of the Ecological Tax Reform. Until then, we suggest that the income should be used for the following purposes:

- Promotion of renewable energy.
- Specific promotion of and support for rational energy use.
- Covering the costs of structural change (re-education).
- External costs of electricity generation.

Presentation of the Report

3.11. International Co-ordination

3.11.1. Question

What is being done by those responsible in order to promote the application of Swiss goals - with appropriate frames of reference - at an international level?

- a) Which concepts exist for European and International electricity supply systems?
- b) How are activities co-ordinated?

3.11.2. Main experts consulted

- Martin Renggli (Swiss Federal Office of Energy, Head of Energy Policy)
- Andreas Wagner (Consultant for Energy and Environmental Policy, mostly active for the European Union)

3.11.3. Summary of experts' answers

The co-ordination of Swiss efforts in the international sphere is carried out within the framework of Switzerland's membership of - and work for - the International Energy Agency, the Energy Charter, the Convention for Climate Protection and the GATT / WTO Agreement. Also, EU programmes and guidelines are taken into consideration when implementing Swiss goals and measures.

- a) *Concepts at a European and international level:* These are for example the European Energy Charter (April 1998), EU internal market guidelines for electricity (1996) as well as the White Paper on renewable energy and the European guideline on electricity delivery.
- b) *Co-ordination of international concepts:* This involves a complicated interplay of international organisations, for example the European Commission, the European Parliament, the Ministers' Council and the governments of member

countries as well as important trade partners, individual interest groups and lobbies.

3.11.4. Citizens' position

It can be noted that our existing and future goals and measures are compatible with European and international guidelines. Switzerland is, however, only a small global village in a big world. Environmental protection knows no frontiers and cannot be held up by them. Usable international concepts are available, but not yet politically implemented: conflicts of interest have stopped this up till now. In spite of our present and future leader-role in certain areas, our influence world-wide is very small. There is, however, a necessity for long-term global solutions and methods of control in the area of electricity generation.

3.11.5. Suggestions

The Citizen Panel demands that Switzerland quickly introduces sustainable solutions, even if they do not meet the ideals of internationally harmonised, high-level energy and environment policy.

The attractiveness of Switzerland as a place to do business should not be detrimentally affected by too much perfection.

4. Programme

Friday 15th May (National Council Chamber, Houses of Parliament)

10:00 - 10:30	<p>Official opening of the PubliForum</p> <p>Opening speeches by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ernst Leuenberger (President of the National Council)</i> • <i>Verena Meyer (President of the Swiss Science Council)</i> • <i>Hans-Ulrich Fischer (National Councillor, President of the Committee for Environment, Area Planning and Energy (UREK))</i>
10:30 - 11:00	<p>What's PubliForum all about?</p> <p>The organisers explain the course of events in the PubliForum</p> <p>The Citizen Panel introduce themselves and explain the topics to be discussed</p>
11:00 - 16:30	<p>Start of the discussions between experts and citizens</p>
<i>11:00 - 11:30</i>	Who can guarantee an "intact" environment with respect to the risks involved in generating electricity? Which ways and means (such as financing, steering instruments, legislation etc.) are available in order to guarantee an "intact" environment?
<i>11:30 - 12:00</i>	How safely and with what responsibility is the disposal of radioactive wastes and the nuclear power plant shut down later to be dealt with? How can the general public contribute to a solution?
<i>12:00 - 14:00</i>	Lunch
<i>14:00 - 14:30</i>	Shouldn't an energy production and supply system consider ethical principles?
<i>14:30 - 15:00</i>	What's possibilities do we have in order to reduce electricity consumption? With which methods can we use and which measures must be put into practice?

<i>15:00 - 15:30</i>	Break
<i>15:30 - 16:30</i>	From which date on and to what proportion can future electricity consumption be met by renewable or alternative energy technologies?
16:30 - 17:30	Discussion
from 19:00	The Citizen Panel retires to look back on the day's work and to summarise the first day.

Saturday 16th May 1998 (Casino Berne, "Burgerratssaal")

09:00 - 12:00	Continuation of the discussion between experts and citizens
<i>09:00 - 09:45</i>	What are the consequences of market liberalisation for the consumer?
<i>09:45 - 10:15</i>	How can all costs incurred, including external ones, be integrated in the price of electricity?
<i>10:15 - 10:45</i>	Break
<i>10:45 - 11:15</i>	What influence would an electricity price increase caused by the introduction of a incentive tax or other forms of energy tax have on the job situation? How would the competitiveness of Swiss businesses be affected?
<i>11:15 - 11:45</i>	What is being done by those responsible in order to promote the application of Swiss goals - with appropriate frames of reference - at an international level?
14:00 - 16:00	Discussion with a speech by Dori Schaer-Born (Councillor of the canton of Berne)
from 16:00	The Citizen Panel retires and begins with the edition of their report containing its recommendations

Monday, 18th May 1998 (Casino Berne, "Burgerratssaal")

- 10:00 - 11:00** **The main results of the PubliForum**
The Citizen Panel presents its report
- 11:00 - 11:30** **Reactions**
Some personalities make comments on the report and on the way the PubliForum worked:
- *Thomas Leisinger (Member of the TA-Steering Committee)*
 - *René Longet (President of the PubliForum's Accompanying Group)*
 - *Brigitta Gadiant (National Councillor, President of the Commission for Science, Education and Culture)*
- 11:30 - 12:15** **Open discussion**
The general public is invited to ask the Panel questions and discuss the contents of the report.
- 12:15** **Closing speech**
by Sergio Bellucci, Head of Switzerland's TA-Programme
- 12:30 - 13:00** **Press-conference**
- Main results in a nut-shell
 - Question-time with the participating citizens and others involved in the PubliForum

5. List of Experts

<i>Name</i>	<i>Organisation</i>
Nissim Chaim	Contratom, Green Party
Jean-François Dupont	General Secretary Communauté Electricité Romande
Georg Erdmann	TU Berlin, Head of the Expert Group for Energy Systems
Regula Gysler	Physicians for the Environment
Markus Häring	Häring Geo-projects
Stefan Hirschberg	Paul Scherrer Institute
Joel Jakubec	President of the Appeal of Geneva APAG
Pierre Lehmann	Association for environmental studies SEDE SA
Peter Marbert	Deputy Head of Infrastructure Department Basel, Novartis Services AG
Roland Naegelin	President of the National Commission on Nuclear Safety
Toni Püntener	Zurich Energy Consulting
Martin Renggli	Swiss Federal Office of Energy, Head of Energy Policy
Hans-Ulrich Schärer	Swiss Federal Office of Energy, renewable energy
Silva Samadeni	National Councillor, Social Democrats

<i>Name</i>	<i>Organisation</i>
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Fritjof Staiss	Centre for Solar Energy and Hydrogen Research (ZSW), Stuttgart
Rudolf Strahm	National Councillor, Social Democrats
Andreas Wagner	German Association for Wind Energy, European Consultant for Energy and Environmental Policy
Rolf Wüstenhagen	Scientific collaborator, Institute for Business and Ecology, HSG
Piet Zuidema	Nagra, departmental head of Nuclear Technology and Safety

Experts state their position in response to citizens' questions

6. Accompanying Group, Organising Staff and Evaluators

	<i>Name</i>	<i>Organisation / Function</i>
<i>Accompanying Group</i>	Irene Aegerter	Swiss Association of Electricity Utilities, Zurich
	Alec Baer	Ex Federal Office of Energy, Berne
	Fulvio Caccia	National Councillor / Member of the TA-Steering Committee, Bellinzona
	Georg Hörning	“Akademie für Technikfolgenabschätzung”, Stuttgart
	Simon Joss	Centre for the Study of Democracy, London
	Emil Kowalski	Nagra, Wettingen / Member of the TA-Steering Committee
	René Longet (President of the Accompanying Group)	Society for the Protection of the Environment, Geneva / Member of the TA-Steering Committee
	Ruedi Meier	Consultant for energy economics, Berne
	Ursula Renold	Swiss Energy Foundation (SES), Zurich
	Rosmarie Waldner	Tages Anzeiger, Zurich
	<i>Name</i>	<i>Organisation / Function</i>

<i>PubliForum Organisation</i>	Michel Baeriswyl	TA / Swiss Science Council Project-assistant PubliForum
	Sergio Bellucci	TA / Swiss Science Council Head of TA-Programme
	Danielle Bütschi	TA / Swiss Science Council Project-leader PubliForum
	Jean-Pierre Hiltbold and team	PUSH'n'PULL / Consulting and communications -support
	Lucienne Rey	TA / Swiss Science Council Public Relations TA-Programme
	Brigitta Walpen	TA / Swiss Science Council TA-Programme Office
<i>Moderation</i>	Ulrich Egger	Egger, Philips + Partner, Zurich
<i>Evaluation</i>	Regula Enderlin-Cavigelli	Risk-Dialogue Foundation, St. Gallen
	Patrick Schild	Risk-Dialogue Foundation, St. Gallen

7. The PubliForum Song

(Melody: Swiss National Anthem. The original is in French)

This is the PubliForum
We are women and also men
like we were in times gone by
when candlelight
was our only form of energy
We looked for better forms
but we still have empty hands
and are confused

We do not know if the heat
of the earth is just a trick to lure us
just as happened, one time before,
with the atomic power stations
these anachronistic left-overs
which we thought couldn't be excelled
these wretched cement tubs
where nothing can be recycled

We do not know if the sun
will ever bring in the lolly
as once was the case
with the lovely thermal power stations
menaced by seismic shocks
So we still look for better things
for a sustainable solution
for a liveable world at last

(by Maryse)

Voici le PubliForum
C'est des femes et puis des hommes
Autant que c'était le cas autrefois
Quand on n'avait qu'les bougies
Pour tout'forme d'énergie
On a cherché beaucoup mieux (bis)
Mais on est resté bredouilles
Et tout plein d'embrouilles.

On n'sait pas si la chaleur
De la terre n'est pas une leurre
Autant que c'était le cas, autrefois
Pour les centrales atomiques
Ces vestiges anachroniques
Qu'on a cru qu'y avait rien d'mieux (bis)
Qu'ces bacs de ciment minables
Où y a rien de recyclable.

On n'sait pas si le soleil
Nous fera gagner de l'oseille
Autant que c'était le cas, autrefois
Pour les belles centrales thermiques
Menacées de secousses sismiques
Alors nous cherchons bien mieux (bis)
Une solution durable
Pour un monde enfin vivable